

TEACHERS COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT AND COMMITMENT: ITS IMPACT TO SCHOOL DEVELOPMENT IN THE DISTRICT OF CANDELARIA QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to find out the relationship of teachers' community involvement and commitment to the school performance among fifty (150) elementary teachers in the district of Candelaria, Quezon. descriptive design has been used and purposive sampling has been used in the study. The findings of the study were the respondents' extent of involvement be described to the community in in terms of development of school plant and facilities, generating resources are both interpreted "highly involved "and community mobilization verbally interpreted of "involved" the extent of teacher's commitment be described in terms of work values, resources mobilization, love of work and professional goal are all verbally interpreted as "highly committed" and the respondents perceive school development in the following such as accountability , leadership and good governance are all verbally interpreted "highly effective. There is a positive significant relationship between teachers' community involvement and commitment and school development and there is positive significant relationship between the teacher's commitment and school development. The researcher concluded that the involvement of community in school plant and facilities, generating resources and community mobilization were highly evident, the teacher's commitment as to work values, resources mobilization, love of work and professional growth were highly extend, the school development such as accountability, transparency, leadership and good governance were highly evident and there is a positive significant relationship between teachers' community involvement and commitment and school development and there is positive significant relationship between the teacher's commitment and school development thus, the hypotheses were rejected.

Keywords: Teachers, Community Involvement, Commitment, School Development